

An analysis of Hospital Service Quality (HSQ) by studying the two major private Hospitals of Raipur city of Chhattisgarh

Dr. Altaf Yousuf Mir¹, Dr. Satya Kishan², Dr. Ila Dixit³, Dr. Shivani Guru⁴, Dr. Bhanu Prasad Behera⁵

¹Associate Professor & Associate Dean – Placement & Alumni Relations, Department of Hospital Management, International Institute of Health Management Research, IIHMR, New Delhi, India, altaf@iihmrdelhi.edu.in

²Assistant Professor, MATS School of Business Studies, MATS University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh

³Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Maharaja Agarsen International College, Raipur, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Amity University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, NIST University, Berhampur, India

KEYWORDS

Service Quality,
Private Hospitals,
OPD & Indoor
Patients, Attendants.

ABSTRACT:

Service quality has been one of the important parameters when we try to achieve the patient satisfaction index. Organizations imparting services particularly related to patient care majorly focus on its quality. Quality of delivery of services is an utmost important tool. Every patient or an attendant of the patient has some perception in his mind or expectation when he visits a hospital regarding the treatment and care provided. If there is a major gap between the service delivery and quality of services, the outcome of the services will be dissatisfaction. If there is no major gap between the two or the quality of services provided meets more than their expectations, the outcome of the services will be highly satisfactory. In this study, a comparative analysis has been done between the two major private hospitals of the Raipur City of Chhattisgarh. The data is primary, and it is collected from the OPD follow-up, indoor patients, and the attendants who visited the hospitals and stayed at least three days for their treatment. (Word count: 170).

1. Introduction

Delivery of the services should meet the needs of the patient and their attendants. Services related to patient care and treatment are of much importance. The focus of corporate hospitals is profitability and simultaneously enhancing the brand image and reputation. Word-of-mouth marketing would be best when the organizations deliver the services at par. The delivery of the services should exceed the expectations of the patient or their attendants. The patient and their attendants are the major stakeholders who avail themselves of the hospital services. The hospital services range from clinical to non-clinical services. Patient feedback or exit interviews are the most common methods or tools used in assessing patient satisfaction. The quality can't be summarized as such as it is affected by numerous factors. The series of events that took place when a patient or the attendant visited the hospital till, he completed his journey of treatment and care.

2. Literature Review

Alghamdi (2014), investigated standard dimensions of SQ, so that the most vital one may be found, he wanted to know about the dimension which is most significantly correlated with the perception. Data was that empathy has a big impact on service quality in-hospital services. According to researchers, this dimension was lacking in public sector hospitals and hence, doctors and other support staff must be trained to understand the emotions and problems of patients. In this study among primary health care centers in Saudi Arabia, most of the respondents felt that a good patient-doctor relationship is the backbone of good quality services.[1]

Suetonia et al. (2014), carried out a study among patients receiving hemodialysis treatment at a government hospital. Their service quality perception was measured to find out the areas of concern. As the process of hemodialysis is long and patients must be in hospital during the process of treatment, their views were important regarding the quality of services, most of the respondents were satisfied with the technical aspects of the process, but there was dissatisfaction among patients regarding the information dissemination and communication with the patients. As the process is long and involves financial burdens also, most of the patients were of the view that the hospital failed to provide services according to their needs. It was highlighted that in the case of critical services involving a matter of health and life, the hospitals must use a customer orientation strategy to provide a better quality of services.[2]

Pouragha and Zarei (2016), concluded that any positive or negative behavior of a patient reflects the feeling of a patient concerning services received. The objective of any organization is profit maximization and enhancing value, for this purpose, the quality of services must be improved, perception of service quality arises from cognitive judgments and patient satisfaction comes from affective judgments, if there is any gap between the expectations and experiences, there will be lower satisfaction and hence the quality of services perception will also be lower, which will decrease the chances of profitability and sustainability in a competitive environment, so to achieve the two basic objectives for the existence of any service organization being customer-oriented and providing good service, quality is a must for hospitals. [3]

3. Research Methodology

The research has been conducted on two major private hospitals in the Raipur city of Chhattisgarh. Both are tertiary care hospitals with a bed strength of more than 500. The sample size was 500 and the sampling technique used was simple random sampling. The primary data was collected by using a questionnaire. The sample area of the study was.

1. Ramakrishna Care Hospitals
2. NH-MMI, Narayana Super-speciality Hospital

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify and measure the factors of the perceptions among the patients and the attendants selected from two major private hospitals in Raipur City.
2. To identify and measure the factors of the service delivery among the patients and the attendants selected from two major private hospitals in Raipur city.
3. To identify and measure the factors of customer satisfaction among the patients and the attendants selected from two major private hospitals in Raipur city.
4. To compare the factors of perception, service delivery, and customer satisfaction among the patients and the attendants selected from two major private hospitals in Raipur city

4. Results & Discussion

1. Tangibility of services

Table 1 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	TANGIBILITYNHMMI	25.9280	125	3.33886	.29864
	TANGIBILITYRCH	28.5760	125	3.59270	.32134

Table 2 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 TANGIBILITYNHMMI TANGIBILITYRCH	-2.64800	4.69773	.42018	-3.47965	-1.81635	-6.302	124	.0000000

The paired t-test of the tangibility factor showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (28.57) is more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (25.92). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the tangibility of services. The t value is -6.302 & the difference in the mean is statistically strongly significant. The significance level is <0.001.

2. Reliability of services

Table 3 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	RELIABILITYNHMMI	13.8400	125	2.74273	.24532
	RELIABILITYRCH	14.9200	125	1.98624	.17765

Table 4 Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	RELIABILITYNHMMI - RELIABILITYRCH	-1.08000	3.44215	.30788	-1.68937	-.47063	-3.508	124	.001

The paired t-test of the reliability factor showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (14.92) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (13.84). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the reliability of services. The t value is -3.508 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is 0.001.

3. Assurance Factor

Table 4 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	ASSURANCENHMMI	10.1760	125	2.17784	.19479
	ASSURANCERCH	10.9120	125	1.47570	.13199

Table 5 Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	ASSURANCENHMMI - ASSURANCERCH	-.73600	2.49885	.22350	-1.17838	-.29362	-3.293	124	.001

The paired t-test of the assurance showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (10.91) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (10.17). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the assurance of services. The t value is -3.293 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is 0.001.

4. Empathy Factor

Table 6 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	EMPATHYNHMMI	13.8240	125	2.87386	.25705
	EMPATHYRCH	14.6640	125	1.99169	.17814

Table 7 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
					Mean	Mean			
Pair 1 EMPATHYNHMMI EMPATHYRCH		-.84000	3.32731	.29760	-1.42904	-.25096	-2.823	124	.006

The paired t-test of the empathy showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (14.66) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (13.82). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the empathy of services. The t value is -2.823 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

5. Responsiveness Factor

Table 8 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 RESPONSIVENESSNHMMI	11.5520	125	1.73417	.15511
RESPONSIVENESSRCH	12.2800	125	1.59940	.14305

Table 9 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
					Mean	Mean			
Pair 1 RESPONSIVENESSNHMMI RESPONSIVENESSRCH		-.72800	2.39413	.21414	-1.15184	-.30416	-3.400	124	.001

The paired t-test of the responsiveness showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (12.28) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (11.55). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the empathy of services. The t value is -3.400 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is 0.001.

6. Admission Process

Table 10 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 ADMISSIONPROCESSNHMMI	16.0960	125	2.54769	0.22787
ADMISSIONPROCESSRCH	16.7120	125	2.11300	0.18899

Table 11 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 ADMISSIONPROCESNHMMI ADMISSIONPROCESRCH	-.61600	3.28188	.29354	-1.19700	-.03500	-2.099	124	.038

The paired t-test of the admission process showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.71) is almost equal to the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (16.09). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are slightly more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the admission process. The t value is -2.099 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

7. Nursing services

Table 12 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 NURSINGSERVICESNHMMI	10.6640	125	2.11730	.18938
NURSINGSERVICESRCH	11.0080	125	1.64364	.14701

Table 13 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 NURSINGSERVICESNHMMI NURSINGSERVICESRCH	-.34400	2.55616	.22863	-.79652	.10852	-1.505	124	.135

The paired t-test of the nursing services showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (11.00) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (10.66). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the nursing services. The t value is -1.505 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

8. Medical Services

Table 14 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 MEDICALSERVICESMI	11.0720	125	2.07976	.18602
MEDICALSERVICESRCH	11.6560	125	1.39182	.12449

Table 15 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 MEDICALSERVICES NHMMI MEDICALSERVICES RCH	-.58400	2.55641	.22865	-1.03657	-.13143	-2.554	124	.012

The paired t-test of the medical services showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (11.65) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (11.07). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the medical services. The t value is -2.554 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

9. Lab and diagnostics services

Table 15 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	LABANDDIAGNOSTICNHMMI	17.0000	125	2.67304	.23908
	LABANDDIAGNOSTICRCH	16.8640	125	2.09586	.18746

Table 16 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 LABANDDIAGNOSTIC NHMMI LABANDDIAGNOSTIC RCH	.13600	3.71428	.33222	-.52155	.79355	.409	124	.683

The paired t-test of the lab and diagnostics showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (17.00). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.86) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the lab and diagnostic services. The t value is .409 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

10. Patient care

Table 17 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	PATEINTCARENHMMI	18.2640	125	3.11123	.27828
	PATEINTCARERCH	19.9520	125	2.47196	.22110

Table 18 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 PATEINTCARENHMMI PATEINTCARERCH	-1.68800	4.01492	.35911	-2.39877	-.97723	-4.701	124	.0000

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 HOUSEKEEPINGNHMMI HOUSEKEEPINGRCH	-.62400	3.01251	.26945	-1.15731	-.09069	-2.316	124	.022

The paired t-test of the patient care showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (19.95) is more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (18.26). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding patient care services. The t value is -4.701 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is < 0.001.

11. Housekeeping Services

Table 19 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 HOUSEKEEPINGNHMMI	11.1520	125	2.18151	.19512
HOUSEKEEPINGRCH	11.7760	125	1.84856	.16534

The paired t-test of the housekeeping showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (11.77) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (11.15). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding patient care services. The t value is -2.316 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

12. Food services

Table 20 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 FOODSERVICESNHMMI	11.7600	125	1.98136	.17722
FOODSERVICESRCH	11.2640	125	1.72806	.15456

Table 21 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 FOODSERVICESNHMMI FOODSERVICESRCH	-.49600	2.77554	.24825	-.00464	.98736	1.998	124	.048

The paired t-test of the food services showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (11.76). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (11.26) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the food services. The t-value is 1.998 & the difference in the mean is not statistically significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

13. Security services

Table 22 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	SECURITYSERVICESNHMMI	15.7600	125	3.02516	.27058
	SECURITYSERVICESRCH	16.8560	125	1.97853	.17697

Table 23 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
					Mean	Std. Deviation			
Pair 1	SECURITYSERVICESNHMMI SECURITYSERVICESRCH	-1.09600	3.63545	.32516	-1.73959	-.45241	-3.371	124	.001

The paired t-test of the security services showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.85) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (15.76). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the security services. The t value is -3.371 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is < 0.001.

14. Medical care

Table 24 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	MEDICALCARENHMMI	16.8720	125	1.92595	.17226
	MEDICALCARERCH	16.4320	125	1.97295	.17647

Table 25 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
					Mean	Std. Deviation			
Pair 1	MEDICALCARENHMMI MEDICALCARERCH	.44000	2.87761	.25738	-.06943	.94943	1.710	124	.090

The paired t-test of the food services showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (16.87). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.43) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the food services. The t value is 1.710 & the difference in the mean is statistically approaching significance. The significance level is < 0.1.

15. Availability Factor

Table 26 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	AVAILABILITYNHMMI	26.2480	125	2.34058	.20935
	AVAILABILITYRCH	25.4960	125	2.50040	.22364

Table 27 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 AVAILABILITYNHMMI AVAILABILITYRCH	-.75200	3.30361	.29548	-.16716	1.33684	2.545	124	.012

The paired t-test of the availability showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (26.24). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (25.49) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the availability of the clinical and non-clinical services of the hospital. The t value is 2.545 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is $> .001$.

16. Professionalism Factor

Table 28 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 PROFESSIONALISMNHMMI	16.7120	125	1.89573	.16956
PROFESSIONALISM RCH	16.4960	125	1.89492	.16949

Table 29 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 PROFESSIONALISMNHMMI PROFESSIONALISM RCH	-.21600	2.71669	.24299	-.26494	.69694	.889	124	.376

The paired t-test of professionalism showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (16.71). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.49) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the professionalism of the doctors and the nursing staff of the hospital. The t value is 0.889 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is $> .001$.

17. Hospital Personnel

Table 30 Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 HOSPITALPERSONNELNHMMI	11.9440	125	1.75198	.15670
HOSPITALPERSONNEL RCH	12.1600	125	1.70104	.15215

Table 31 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 HOSPITALPERSONNELNHMMI HOSPITALPERSONNEL RCH	-.21600	2.36433	.21147	-.63456	.20256	-1.021	124	.309

The paired t-test of the hospital personnel showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (12.16) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (11.94). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the hospital personnel. The t value is -1.021 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

18. Technical Quality

Table 32 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	TECHNICALQUALITYNHMMI	49.5120	125	5.90464	.52813
	TECHNICALQUALITYRCH	46.9440	125	4.43466	.39665

Table 33 Paired Samples Test

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	TECHNICALQUALITYNHMMI TECHNICALQUALITYRCH	-2.56800	7.75568	.69369	1.19499	3.94101	3.702	124	.000

The paired t-test of the technical quality showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (49.51). is more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (46.94) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the technical quality of the hospital. The t-value is 3.702 & the difference in the mean is statistically significant. The significance level is < .001.

19. Administrative Care

Table 34 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	ADMINISTRATIVECARENHMMI	38.7920	125	2.63137	.23536
	ADMINISTRATIVECARERCH	38.8480	125	2.85413	.25528

Table 35 Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences		Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation		Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	ADMINISTRATIVECARENHMMI ADMINISTRATIVECARERCH	-.05600	3.90885	.34962	-.74799	.63599	-.160	124	.873

The paired t-test of the hospital personnel showed the mean value of the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (38.84) is slightly more than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (38.79). This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Ramakrishna Care Hospital are more satisfied than the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital regarding the administrative care of the hospital. The t value is -.160 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > 0.001.

20. Diagnostics Factor

Table 36 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	DIAGNOSTICSNHMMI	8.3120	125	1.18741	.10620
	DIAGNOSTICSRCH	8.1200	125	1.20884	.10812

Table 37 Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	DIAGNOSTICSNHMMI DIAGNOSTICSRCH	-.19200	1.70245	.15227	-.10939	.49339	1.261	124	.210

The paired t-test of the diagnostics showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (8.31) is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (8.12) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the diagnostics facilities of the hospital. The t value is 1.261 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > .001.

21. Communication Factor

Table 38 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	COMMUNICATIONNHMMI	16.8080	125	1.85653	.16605
	COMMUNICATIONRCH	16.3440	125	2.18538	.19547

Table 39 Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	COMMUNICATIONNHMMI COMMUNICATIONRCH	-.46400	3.01487	.26966	-.06973	.99773	1.721	124	.088

The paired t-test of the diagnostics showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (16.80) is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (16.34) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the communication facilities of the hospital. The t value is 1.721 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > .001.

22. Interaction Factor

Table 40 Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	INTERACTIONNHMMI	26.5120	125	2.36444	.21148
	INTERACTIONRCH	26.1040	125	2.38552	.21337

Table 41 Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 INTERACTIONNHM MI INTERACTIONRCH	26.40800	3.41273	.30524	-.19616	1.01216	1.337	124	.184

The paired t-test of the interaction showed the mean value of the Narayana Hridulaya – MMI Hospital (26.51). is slightly more than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital (26.10) This shows that the patients (indoor & OPD) and the attendants visiting Narayana Hridulaya – MMI hospital are more satisfied than the Ramakrishna Care Hospital regarding the interaction facilities of the hospital. The t value is 1.337 & the difference in the mean is statistically not significant. The significance level is > .001.

5. Conclusion

This study has been conducted on two major private hospitals in the Raipur city of Chhattisgarh. When we see the comparative analysis between the two major players there is not much difference in the means. That means both hospitals are working well as far as the quality of services is concerned. But there is always scope for improvement. Taking regular patient feedback and conducting exit interviews will let the organization know where they are lacking and areas for improvement. How the grievance is handled and resolved. The management has a big role in this area as they are most concerned about the reputation and brand image of the hospital.

References:

- [1] Alghamdi, S.F. The impact of service quality perception on patient satisfaction in Government hospitals in Southern Saudi Arabia, Saudi Med Journal; 2014, 35 (10):1271-1273.
- [2] Suetonia, P.C., Giorgia, B., Jonathan, C., Allison, T., Marcello, T. and Fabio, P., Patient Satisfaction with Haemodialysis Care: An International Survey. Journal of American Medical Association, 2014, 4(2), 76-85.
- [3] Pouragha, B. And Zarei, E., The Effect of Outpatient Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction in Teaching Hospitals in Iran, Materia socio Medica, 2016, 28(2), 21-25.
- [4] Pai, P.Y. and Chary, S.T., (2013), Dimensions of Hospital Service Quality: A Critical Review: Perspective of Patients from Global Studies, International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance, 26(4), 308-340,
- [5] Padma, P., Rajendran, C., & Lokachari, P. S. (2010). Service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction in Indian hospitals: Perspectives of patients and their attendants. Benchmarking: An International Journal, 17(6), 807–841. doi:10.1108/14635771011089746